

Discursive Construction At Work: Representation of Masculinity in Women's Magazines of 1980s*

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Abstract: This article discusses the discursive construction of the ideal male subject in women's magazines published in the 1980s, when Turkey was going through a significant transformation process. In contrast to studies that analyze the representation of masculinity in men's magazines or femininity in women's magazines, this article offers a different perspective to understanding the socio-cultural context by focusing on representations of men in women's magazines. The topics directly related to men in *Kadınca* and *Elele*, monthly magazines published throughout the 1980s, were analyzed through critical discourse analysis. All issues of the magazines published between 1980 and 1990 were examined and included in the analysis. The magazines' construction of the ideal male subject involves discourse strategies that emphasize change, centralize moving away from traditional values and objectify the male body. This construction is often accompanied by the inversion of emotions and virtues. In this context, the ideal male subject in magazines represents a modern, secular and middle-class masculinity.

Keywords: Masculinity, Critical Discourse Analysis, Sociology of Emotions, 1980s.

Introduction

The transformation of manhood has been under discussion for some time under women's studies and masculinity literature (Farrell, 1974; Connell, 1987; Butler, 1990; Edward, 2006). These studies, which question social patterns around the roles given to women and men, emphasize that masculinity, like femininity, is social and contextual. The emphasis of feminism that gender roles are determined by culture, not biological, draws attention to the culturally constructed dimensions of masculinity (Yücel, 2014; 41). Masculinity studies, which emerged as an independent field since the mid-1990s, discusses how masculine identities are constructed from many aspects (Horzum, 2018: 76). The social constructionist perspective that has emerged in masculinity studies since the 1980s emphasizes the importance of paying attention to the existence of different types of masculinity formed in the light of parameters such as religion, class, race and education (Okutan, 2017: 21). On the other hand, discussing class and gender relations together constitutes one of the key points for understanding different types of masculinities and power relations (Sancar, 2008:43). The

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masculinity discussed in this study represents an urban, middle class, secular masculinity based on the rise of the new middle classes in the 1980s.

In the rapidly changing socio-cultural environment of the 1980s, especially with the discussion of male authority, the family and the institution of marriage, a discourse of change also emerged on the ideal male subject. The 1980s, when women's magazine publishing in Turkey underwent a transformation under the influence of popular feminist discourse, witnessed a rising emphasis on changing masculinity within this discourse. The second-wave feminism's emphasis on inequalities within the private sphere, which is summarized with the slogan "the personal is political", and the emphasis that these are not individual experiences (see Hanisch, 1970) has opened up questions about domestic roles and inequalities, especially sexuality.

Women's magazines have long been one of the important areas of study in the literature from many different aspects such as defining, transforming, objectifying women or creating a female identity (Ballaster et al., 1991). While these studies, which generally focus on female subjects in magazines, deal with the way women are represented in magazines, the limited studies that focus on specific male representations in Turkey (Kirca-Schroeder, 2007; Yalın, 2012) do not cover the period and questions discussed in this article. However, the way men are represented in women's magazines is also an important element that helps to analyze the socio-cultural context and to comprehend it more holistically. Popular women's magazines, which mostly appeal to female readers and construct the female subject, exhibit and transform the ways in which women make sense not only of themselves but also of the opposite sex and their environment.

This article focuses on two popular monthly women's magazines that continued to be published throughout the 80s. *Kadınca*, which began publication in 1978, is the first popular feminist magazine in Turkey. As a reflection of the feminism that became popular in Turkey from the 1980s onwards (Kirca-Schroeder, 2007), *Kadınca* publishes pioneering publications for the modernization and emancipation of women. In doing so, it seeks to transform men and relationships as much as women. In this transformation, the struggle against traditional society and values is a key element and this struggle involves a redefinition of virtues and emotions. Launched in 1976, *Elele*, a monthly women's magazine, was first published as a family magazine and focuses on issues such as maternal and infant health. Over time, the magazine became dominated by *tabloid* language and topics parallel to the transformation process of the 1980s. In this process of change, both the way the magazine defines ideal fatherhood and especially the Playgirl supplements it started to publish in 1987 provide important data for this article.

Sexuality constitutes one of the most important dimensions for the media in the social context of the 1980s, which became apolitical after the coup and turned towards the private sphere. The prominence of sexuality has two different dimensions that are important for this study. The first of these is the use and provocation of sexuality as a commercial element by the media, and the other is the emphasis on sexuality as a means of emancipation by the women's movement that revived in that period. The fact that female sexuality was first represented in popular culture products after 1980 (Kirca-Schroeder, 2007: 91) sheds light on the second important dimension of sexuality. In parallel

with the spread of second wave feminism in Turkey, sexual freedom constituted almost the most important dimension of women's emancipation in the 1980s. In particular, the publications of *Kadınca* around sexuality coincide with this discourse. While the magazine invites women to recognize, question and enjoy their own sexuality, it constructs this as an element of emancipation. This situation paves the way for a discursive transformation that includes both the change of relationships involving extramarital affairs and the treatment of the male body as a sexual object, while constructing the ideal male subject.

This article discusses the transformation of masculinity through a critical discourse analysis (CDA) of the ideal male subject presented in *Elele* and *Kadınca*. CDA is an approach which includes several different methodological approaches and considers language as a social practice and focuses more on social inequality and discourses as tools that construct or legitimize them (Wodak, 2001: 4). CDA focuses more on structural features than other discourse types that emphasize the interactional dimension of speech (Arkonaç, 2014: 173). For the CDA, which takes into account the social context that constructs the discourse, language analysis is also to analyze the process of interaction. As one of the pioneers of the CDA Fairclough (2001: 126) points out that interaction includes not only conversations but also forms of interaction, such as newspaper reports, where the interactors are at a distance. Through magazine analysis in which the interactants are distanced, this article adopts the CDA's characteristic of drawing attention to structural features by focusing on the socio-cultural structure of the 1980s, highlighting the way in which discourse is both reflective and transformative of culture. In CDA, how discourse is constructed is discussed through the analysis of many aspects such as the words used, the emphases, the headlines highlighted, the biased discourses hidden in the text etc. In this article, I draw attention to these dimensions and focus mainly on the discursive strategies and techniques that construct texts. Therefore, in the analysis, I centered on Foucault's concept of discursive strategy (2002: 71) and Ardiç's (2012: 311) concept of discursive technique, which mean sub-tiers of strategies.

There are three discourse strategies in this regard: "presenting the change of men as an ideal beyond fact", "Constructing the man who moves away from traditional male roles as the ideal man" "Objectification of the male body as an element of equality". The first strategy is supported by the discursive techniques of "linking men's change to women's change" and "highlighting men who do housework or childcare". The second strategy is supported by the discursive techniques of "presenting men's views on issues such as marriage, chastity, virtue" and "presenting examples of "open-minded" husbands and fathers". The third strategy is supported by the discursive technique of "inverting the language used in the objectification of the female body". The emphasis on a mentality change beyond the regulations on men is at the center of these strategies and techniques. This mentality change is a process that is expected to take place starting from the idea that the traditional values that need to be fought are produced by and in favor of men. Thus, the reproduction of the male subject is a part of the struggle with society. This analysis aims to offer a new perspective that combines the methods of the sociology of emotions and the sociology of religion by including the transformation of emotions and values in the discussion. Because, in the process of Turkey's great

sosyo-cultural transformation in the 1980s, there was also a transformation in the definition of emotions and values such as strength, courage, love, pride and shame.

New Fathers, New Husbands, New Partners

There are two important issues in the discourse on men's change: First, the works that are seen as women's responsibility in the traditional society, such as chores and childcare, are started to be undertaken by men. The second is the emphasis that the character of the men have softened, their authority over their wives and daughters has diminished, and they have begun to become more "open-minded". For the first, interviews with famous fathers who take care of their children, spend time with them, and take care of them are included.

On the cover of the March 1981 issue of *Elele*, there is a spot that says "dads can do mothering too". The subject, which is presented with the title of "Fathers' silent revolution" in the content, first draws attention to the differences between theory and practice in the father-child relationship and the conflict between the emotional desires of fathers and their professional obligations. While emphasizing that fathers are now starting to spend more time with their children and "lightening the burden of their wives", the article also criticizes fatherhood, which focuses on factors such as football, cars and television instead of spending time with their children, even on weekends. The article, published anonymously but written by a man², presents the two fathers as an example with the headline "our revolutionary fathers". In the interviews with theater artist Müşfik Kenter and Law Faculty assistant Levent Bıçakçı, half of the 5-page article consists of photographs, and there are images of fathers driving baby carriages, feeding their children, dressing them, and reading a book by their cradle. While these photographs reinforce the image of changing fathers, the phrase "revolutionary" in the title points to the perception of fatherhood embedded in the socio-cultural structure of the 1980s. The frequent emphasis and affirmation of this change is one of the factors that trigger change and exemplifies the discursive strategy "presenting the change of men as an ideal beyond fact".

In this context the domestic duties and responsibilities of men are opened up for discussion with articles such as "Sir, Don't Avoid the Dish" (May 1982); "Every father is a little bit of a mother!" (November 1983); "Where are those old fathers?" (January 1984). In this period, *Elele* maintains its educational position in child care. For this reason, issues such as the father's role in child education come to the fore in the articles. Since the second half of the 80s, it is possible to talk about the change in the language used with the effect of tabloidization and the shift to gender equality in the handling of the issues.

In the article titled "This is what you call a father" (June 1986), three fathers are introduced on the occasion of Father's Day. The first spot in the article is as follows:

² In the text, there are statements referring to his wife and mentioning men as fellow human beings.

Men are slowly changing now. Where are the pashas of the past who stretched out their feet and asked for even their water from their spouses! Where are the modern fathers who are willing to even share the childcare with his wife now!

In the 1980s, when almost everything changed rapidly, the change of men is also a part of social reality. However, magazines use it as a discursive strategy to promote change by highlighting a limited number of examples. Here, in the first two pages of the four-page article, Zeynep Özal's wife Asım Ekren is presented as one of the ideal father examples, while the narrative is covered with *tabloid* news such as the family's love for the baby, how the house is furnished, the weight of the baby, the flower he sent to his mother on mother's day, and the dimple in his chin from his grandfather Turgut Özal. On the other hand, the phrase "Asım Ekren in short, a modern father with awareness of paternity" in the spotlight redefines the modern male subject by referring to the tension between traditional and modern. The subheadings for the exemplary fathers presented on the other pages are Cihat Soyhan "Is it a henpeck? What does that mean?" and İhsan Altıparmak "A man should do all the work at home". These chapters feature photos of fathers feeding their children or changing their children's diapers. Thus, socially unconventional paternity roles are defined through the discussion of established patterns such as henpeckedness, as in many places in traditional society, these roles are considered shameful behaviors for men.

In the article titled "Modern Men, Old-Fashioned Men" (October 1981) *Kadınca* directly points to the change of men and the conflict between modernity and tradition. This change is brought to the spotlight with the following sentences:

Fortunately today's husband has changed a lot. Men (some of them, of course) are no longer ashamed to help out with the housework. While the despotic and proud husband type of the past is being erased, a nice husband type is formed who does not make it a matter of pride to help his wife at home by keeping up with the times. Some are in the transition period; they help their wives at home, but they don't want to show it to anyone because they think it will be a matter of mockery. When the doorbell rings, they immediately leave the kitchen and take their places in the living room. The man of our time is now looking for a cultured, intelligent, beautiful "life partner" instead of a scruffy, neglected "servant" worn out by housework. The "old-fashioned, anxious" man is gradually being replaced by the "smart" man who does not make helping his wife with the housework a matter of pride... But as we said, slowly... slowly.

As the title of the article indicates, the change in men's roles is a matter of mentality. While the magazine presents changing men as role models to its readers, it defines those who do not keep up with change with titles such as old-fashioned, despotic, and anxious. Thus, with the emphasis of Van Dijk, the biased discourse hidden in the text (2001) emerges in the way the traditional male model is handled. In the article, the characteristics of men who fall into these groups are listed under the headings of "old-fashioned husband" and "modern-minded husband". The first refers to a "traditional" man who sees his wife as a robot and is uncomfortable even with her being listened to, and the second refers to a man with a modern view, "raised from an enlightened class", and a man who values his wife and ideas. The ideal wife for the "modern-minded husband" category is not one who does housework all the time, but one who "sits across, well-groomed and dressed up", "tells him something interesting" and "drinks together". Thus, both the ideal male subject and the ideal female

subject are redefined. On the other hand, these definitions are extremely class-based. While secular practices such as alcohol consumption stand out as an element of modern togetherness, features such as well-groomedness and good dressing correspond to middle-class practices. While emphasizing that the process of change takes place with the new generation, the article ends with the statement "Now, the whole problem is to chasten the old ones those who are stubborn in sticking to the old traditions...". Thus, *Kadınca* undertakes the task of bringing men to their knees as it does in many other issues related to gender equality.

A few years later, *Kadınca* points out that the change of men takes place depending on the change of women repeating the same process with the question "Have Men Changed?" (April, 1986) and operates the discursive strategy of "constructing the man who moves away from traditional male roles as the ideal man".

Believe it or not, men are changing. Because the woman is no longer the former woman. Some men are adapting to this change. Some of them are surprised. They oscillate between the old and the new. Some of them, on the other hand, do not change because they are men by birth, and they insist on practicing the profession of masculinity. Let's see what will happen in the end?

Based on the changing representations of men in cinema, literature and television, the article draws attention to the transition from a strong male model to a softer male model based on the differences between Clark Gable and Robert de Niro. Since women no longer prefer strong men who don't make mistakes and don't cry, ordinary male types are becoming more common. In other words, it is women who change and thus change men. *Kadınca* (September 1986) repeats this change and implements discursive techniques of "linking men's change to women's change" that came with women in her article titled "Women's Secret Desire a "Pretty Bad Boy":

Once upon a time there was a "Prince Charming" ... Women would wait for him... Only he could save them from evil, misery, and "witches"... Women could not cope with all these difficulties alone... Then one day, women saw that they could cope with difficulties... They forgot about Prince Charming. ... Women now wanted freedom, not humility... Together, hand in hand, but free... "Prince Charming" was replaced by "pretty bad boy"... Cheerful, excited, witty, nice, handsome, free "pretty bad boy" ... "Pretty bad boy" settled in the hearts and souls of women, their longing grew... it grew... "Pretty bad boy" is still in deep down of women...

By appealing to a female readership, the magazine also shows its readers the male model to be admired. The article is about a woman who is married but falls in love with another man, who is described as a pretty bad boy, about her desire to go with that man, but her inability to go. The monotony of marriage instead of an exciting life that she will live with him is narrated. Thus, being excited prevents a secure coupling. Instead of values such as love, respect and trust, elements such as desire, excitement and freedom come to the fore. Here, there is a discourse about men and women changing, as well as their relationships.

Kadınca (October 1986) constructs the change of men through the change of women as an identity crisis with the article titled, "What left for the man?". At the beginning of each paragraph, what men did in the past is indicated in bold, and then it is explained that today women and the changes in conditions have begun to lose their validity.

In the past, men were to marry with

In the past, it was possible to have children thanks to men.

In the past, men used to feed the house.

In the past, men used to protect women from hardships.

In the past, men were a measure of value for women.

In the past, men used to rule women.

In the past, men used to beautify the world with their art.

In the past, men used to not fluster in bed

In the past, men used to be kind to women.

These titles emphasize, that men are not dominant in the world of women who earn their own money, are self-confident, know martial arts, use their minds, are free in sexual experience, and do their own business, choose to be single, do not want to have children and know artificial insemination methods. In this new world, men are in the position of companions accompanying women. The sentences above, "Men used to beautify the world with their art" and "Men used to be kind to women", which seem positive at first glance, are also negative features in their explanations. The first indicates that not only men but also women make the world beautiful, and the second indicates that as women get stronger, politeness such as lighting their cigarettes and meeting their needs is a thing of the past.

Kadınca (Ocak 1987) published a quiz for men titled "Let's see if you are the ideal man" with the spotlight consisting of these sentence:

Women have undergone a great change. Of course, you claim to be an expert in their exchange. You learned to ask them "how is your work?" instead of asking "how is your mother?". You also learned to let them know when you come home late in the evening or even to ask for permission... But you still get confused from time to time and you can't guess what's going on in their minds, admit it! It's normal, it can happen! ... Take the quiz and see if you are the ideal man of our time, or rather, the day we live in.

For each of the options presented in the test, women's opinions on the subject are conveyed with percentages, at the end of the test. Thus, the transformation in this direction is encouraged by conveying the characteristics of the ideal man from the eyes of women. The test also offers women the possibility to measure how well their own relationship and tastes match what is considered ideal, by learning the opinions of their fellows. Thus, for example, the information that a man who can't control his tears from time to time is loved more than a man who hides his feelings and always seems cheerful is transferred to the readers. This transfer serves to construct the desirable subject. A new ideal male subject emerges, who replaces the strong, unwavering man in harmony with the whole of the magazine.

Within the framework of this relationship, the man who takes titles ideal, modern, backward/old-fashioned, macho etc. gets closer to the ideal as he moves away from traditional values. Thus, "Constructing the man who moves away from traditional male roles as the ideal man" works as a discursive strategy. These were issues such as women's employment, not getting involved in their partner's dressing, sharing domestic chores and especially virginity at that time. According

to *Kadınca*, the man, who is still at the beginning of the change in this period, continues his traditional roles, especially when it comes to marriage and relationships.

In July 1989, *Kadınca* carried the jealousy of men on the cover with the headline "I'm a man, I'm a macho". In the introductory article of the magazine, Duygu Asena describes a relationship style that women initially liked but became uncomfortable with over time while analyzing the relationship between Western women and Turkish men. Because the Turkish man does not envy his partner because of his love, as it is thought. He acts like this because he thinks he owns her. She writes: "No to oppression, ownership, inhibition. Someone who is already strong does not try to hinder the other person and take away his freedom." These sentences change the definition of strength. In this context, while many concepts such as courage, strength and self-confidence continue to be virtues, how these virtues are defined and what they essentially mean varies according to the socio-cultural context.

Elele (July 1986) features a smiling man wearing a kitchen apron and holding a pan, and a woman hugging him by the waist with the phrase "Elele's great research: Our Men are Changing" on the cover of the magazine. The photo gives a clear message of changing roles in relationships.

Within the magazine the subject titled as "Modern Turkish Man with its Pros and Cons" contains a picture of an unhappy man lying face down tied with a rope and a smiling woman sitting on it. The research, which was conducted in 4 big cities (Istanbul, Ankara, Izmir, Adana), with 40 questions asked to 500 women, states that it only researches "modern Turkish men" due to differences among men. Women between the ages of 20-35 were asked questions for this group, which is defined as "men who have a decisive power in society, who have had an urban culture and at least high school graduates". The summary in bold is as follows:

He is tied to his traditions, but he tries to get rid of some chauvinistic value judgments. He makes an effort to communicate with you about his needs and feelings, but still has trouble opening up from time to time. He is on his way to believe in gender equality, but he does not always show his belief because this [equality] also makes him uncomfortable. Most of them do housework, but avoid doing it in front of others... Many believe in loyalty, but they don't hesitate to make "lechery" jokes. He is sexually obsessed but sometimes feels insecure about sex.

The man of the 1980s, who was emphasized to be in the dilemma between tradition and modernity, has to change in the face of a more active, free and assertive female subject with the rising feminism. In addition to this, the direction of change is determined by showing the ideal male form to men over the expectations of women, while at the same time allowing women to review their expectations of men. For example, in the answer to the question "Do they care about virginity?" the sentences "Looking at the fact that men have come this far, it can be thought that the stories of preferring to marry virgins have now turned into a boring fairy tale." is used. So, men have a path of change to take, and they are just at the beginning of this path. By this way, both the discursive strategies "Presenting the change of men as an ideal beyond fact" and "Constructing the man who moves away from traditional male roles as the ideal man" is executed.

The change of men is also in question for some special practices as well as general qualities. The article titled “Men Does Belly Dance Too” (*Elele*, December 1989) exemplifies this by focusing on men doing belly dance.

Spot: The era is the era of stepping into new age. Since our men are dancing to the tune of all time, they fit in this period. And what a fit... They are advancing by belly dancing, breaking their neck and twisting their hips. It's as if, in spite of women's liberation movements, they say "Will you take our values, we will take yours"... Come on, sixty, seventy, eighty...

While the opinions of men who perform belly dance from many different professions are conveyed in the article, the common message of the views is that men who can do belly dance are modern men. For example, Selami Ertaç says, “So the playing man is a modernized man. Now men have thrown away a lot of pressure from them. They are trying to reach freedom”. In this context, men also get their share of the emancipation discourse, which has become almost the fashion of the period. Thus, emancipation, which means liberation from social pressures by becoming more independent from male-dominated values for women, also works with the process of differentiation from traditional social rules for men. Doing what could not be done in the past and not being afraid of it, is the basis of emancipation.

The words of Mehmet Ali Erbil, among those whose views have been given, point to this issue:

In the past, when men played belly dance, they would say, “**Oh, he's playing like a woman,**” and look at them with criticizing eyes. Now social, cultural and economic comfort has come to our society. People are no longer as shy as they used to be. Men can now play belly dance without shame as before.

In the socio-cultural structure of the 1980s, in which everything that was suppressed, postponed and given up for a purpose was replaced by emancipation and freedom (Gürbilek, 2001: 19), power shapes the society through the discourse of a world of possibilities, which is established on the basis that nothing is the same as before. Being able to do things without shame becomes the basic principle of liberation. On the other hand, some behaviors become shameful. For example, many forms of thought and behavior presented above as a sign of backwardness are shameful for the modern man.

“A Turkish Man Undressed for the First Time”: Presentation of the Male Body

While the construction of the female body in lifestyle magazines has a long history, it has a more recent history for men. The male body, idealized in ancient Greece and Rome, but around the middle of the 1800s, the focus moved to the female body. Grogan presents examples of this historical process, such as the Daedalic-style sculptures of the 7th century BC, the slender, muscular warriors in Roman painting and sculpture, or the nude male sculptures of the Renaissance. In the 1980s and 1990s, when idealized depictions of naked or partially naked males started to appear often in mainstream Western media, the emphasis on the male body returned (Grogan: 1999: 16-17). The magazines I have reviewed here partially convey this transformation in the Western media to Turkey. However, rather than constructing the ideal male figure, these magazines place more focus on establishing the male model as a symbol of equality by upsetting the dynamic between the man looking and the woman being looked at. While for women, courage in the presentation of their body

is an adjective that is mostly used to indicate bodily perfection, when it comes to the male body, courage indicates an adjective in the sense of conflict with social values. For this reason, the magazines' display of the male body takes place within the framework of the discursive strategy of "objectifying the male body as an element of equality" rather than emphasizing bodily perfection.

In her article titled "A Turkish Man Undressed for the First Time" (February 1982), *Kadınca* expresses this situation as follows while publishing nude men's photos as an element of gender equality:

As you've seen in past issues, men in the west undress on stage and pose nude for magazines. Just like women in the west. In our country, it seems as if this is only for women... Because nobody thought that women had the freedom to look at nudity, because nobody suggested Turkish men to do such a job. Here is a civilized and brave Turkish man, İlyas... Take it or leave it; look at it or ignore it...

In essence, the article emphasizes the right of women to watch the naked male body, not the right of men to undress. According to the magazine, it is a matter of choice to look or not, but the important thing is to offer this opportunity. Presenting the nude photos of the model throughout the 6-page article, *Kadınca* also publishes the readers' reactions to the previously published nude male photos.

In one of them, the following lines are included with the title of "Thoughts of a Male Reader":

Ismail Kaygılaroğlu from Galatasaray said, "...I showed the poster of Erkekçe magazine this month to a few of my sincere friends. All found it excellent. I also showed the naked man in *Kadınca*, a quarter of them said "Isn't he ashamed", two-fourths said "it's perfectly normal, most American magazines have such things", and the other quarter reproached (believe me) why they had it censored.

The fact that some of the people who find the erotic female body excellent ask "are they not ashamed" for male photographs is an indication that there isn't principled stance and moral concern regarding the presentation of the body. The display of the male body means the regression from the seer position to the visible position and loss of authority. Karabıyık-Barbarosoğlu (2006) pointed out that the transition of the relationship between seeing and being seen from the vertical plane to the horizontal plane in the postmodern period led to the increase in the value of being seen, while emphasizing that it also changed the authority relations. In the 1980s, the male body was just at the beginning of its existence and control process. Men's lifestyle magazines, which first appeared in Turkey after the 1990s, are presented as a search for an answer to the crisis of masculinity in the face of the changing social structure, women's movement and feminism (Yavuz, 2017). The use of the male body as an object of sexuality and its regulation around beauty standards took place in this process (Erdoğan, 2014; Onay, 2017). As a pioneer in the exhibition of the male body, *Kadınca* developed her discourse against inequality not by opposing the commodification of the female body, but by showing that the male body should also be commodified. By doing this, the magazine expands the sexual discourse of the 1980s. *Kadınca*, continues her presentation of the naked male body with examples such as "Confessions of a Male Prostitute" (May 1982), "Ibo's Nude Protest" (June 1982). One of the striking points in the news of "Ibo's Nude Protest" is that the subtitle of the article is "If Crows Sing, Fats Will Undress". While it is seen that women, who make a reputation by undressing even though their voices are not beautiful, are criticized in the content of the article, in fact, an

accepted truth is admitted: It is absurd for fat people with an “ugly” body to undress, as it is for an ugly voice to sing. However, this is again an absurdity for women. Because it is not a fat woman's body that is on display, but a fat man's body.

In October 1985 with the cover letter "Naked Citizen: Şener Şen", and in July 1988 with the cover letter "Yes When It Comes to Women, No to Naked Men", *Kadınca* carries naked men photos directly to the cover. The second one focuses directly on the leading role of *Kadınca* in displaying the naked male body and the discussions on this subject. The spotlight of the article is as follows:

The female body has been exhibited in every period of history... Women are champions in nudity, while men are always one step behind. However, nowadays men also undress. We are the first to undress men in Turkey, *Kadınca* herself...

The magazine also tries to create awareness in the readers about the action it consciously undertakes. The article starts with the reactions of two photographers, one woman and one man, who take pictures of nude men, and conveys the thoughts of names such as Atilla İlhan, Abdurrahman Dilipak, Nilüfer Göle, Müjde Ar, Bedri Baykam, Burçin Orhon on nudity. The pages of the subject, which has 6 pages, are full of nude or semi-naked men photos. Men giving these poses emphasize that they look at the situation from an aesthetic point of view. For example, while model Engin Koç emphasizes naturalness by saying that there isn't any difference between a woman in a black veil and a naked woman, *Kadınca* gives this expression as a spotlight next to the photograph. On the next page, in a box enclosed in a frame in the middle of the page, the following statements are prominently displayed in bold and colored fonts:

According to experts, men approach their naked fellows with feelings of jealousy and discomfort. Naked men, on the other hand, say that they undress in the name of freedom and modernity.

The statement of “according to experts” presents an objective assessment image rather than a biased presentation and the discussion gains legitimacy. It is stated that 85 out of 100 women interviewed in the article find it positive that men undress. However, it should be assumed that the sample group selected for this rate was heavily influential in the socio-cultural structure of the 1980s. Since no information is provided about this, the rate given only feeds the perception that women expect this as well. While the only view directly against men's undressing is conveyed in the article from Abdurrahman Dilipak, within the limits set by religion on this issue, there are many views that affirm this situation in various aspects, or at least do not find it negative. In one of the interviews with the undressing men, Yılmaz Zafer said, “I posed nude to show that I think freely and modern. In the 20th century, we see naked men and women in cinema. Photography is also a part of cinema. There is nothing to be ashamed of”. Thus, while constructing the discourse, art is used as a means of legitimation. This situation is also directly related to the "explosion of desire" (Gürbilek, 1999: 25) and the discourse of freedom that began to rise in the 1980s. The idea that anyone can do whatever they wish without shame or embarrassment has become central to the discourse of modern Turkey.

Elele, similarly, serves to exhibit nude male bodies with the *Playgirl* supplements it has given in various issues after 1987 (eg. June 1987; August 1987; March 1988; October 1988). In these articles, the same format is applied on the male body by making an ironic criticism of the language

used while displaying female bodies in the media. While the first of these appendices was introduced with the image of a woman carrying a playgirl in a bag, the sentences "Even though this is a dream for now, even if we look at it from a slightly amusing point of view, maybe it is the core of the future Playgirl" clearly expresses this irony (June 1987). These texts, which invert the discourse on the female body and apply it to the male, go beyond the ironic dimension with the photos of half-naked or completely naked men accompanying them, and really expose women to an unusual image. These images are in line with the desire and need for satisfaction that magazines constantly highlight in the context of sexual freedom. However, the encouragement of women to look and see is at the forefront rather than the encouragement of men for bodily presentation. Against the male gaze, whose field is expanding day by day, the woman's view of the man as a sexual object is transferred to the discourse. In this context, the struggle against tradition as an indicator of modernity functions as a discursive strategy.

The subject construction of the magazines focuses on having a middle-class lifestyle in socio-economic terms, while ideologically it is based on a modernist and secular understanding of life. Therefore, the biggest obstacle in the construction of the ideal subject is traditional society and traditional values. This is because traditional social values, especially the moral principles shaped under the influence of religion, are opposed to modern secular morality in many areas such as individualism, exhibitionism, consumption and fashion. Therefore, in Turkey's long modernization adventure, religion, tradition and Easternness function as obstacles to progress as part of the Westernization ideal.

Conclusion

The 1980s represent an important transition period for Turkey, in which political and economic changes were reflected in almost every aspect of socio-cultural life. In this process of change, magazines occupy an important position as transmitters of culture and lifestyles. This article discusses the implications of this transition for the representation of a particular kind of masculinity in women's magazines. This masculinity is a modern, secular and middle-class masculinity in the process of change. Since the magazines analyzed here were the most important representatives of popular feminism at the time, change expresses a desire that goes beyond reality. Thus, while the discursive construction of the ideal man is realized, established social values exist as a field of conflict. This field offers the opportunity to follow the transformation of masculinity on the one hand and to see the main areas of debate of the period on the other.

This article attempts to describe the ideal male subject in women's magazines around three main discursive strategies and the discursive techniques that support them. Accordingly, the ideal male subject, who is still in the process of change, approaches this ideal to the extent that he moves away from traditional society and its values, since traditional society, as the opposite of modernity and secular lifestyle, is the main constructor of gender inequality in favor of men. Therefore, magazines categorize men through adjectives such as modern and old-fashioned, ideal and macho, etc. and present the man women should desire. This modern man is more egalitarian, softer in

character and open-minded. Therefore, he shares responsibilities such as childcare and household chores, and is far from jealousy, interfering with his partner's dress or behavior.

One of the important points about the representation of masculinity in magazines is the presentation of the male body as an object of desire. For the first time in the history of Turkey, photographs of naked men were published in popular publications, signaling both an inversion of social control processes and a conflict with traditional social values. While these publications encourage men to undress and women to look, the narrative is constructed around the rising discourse of freedom in the 1980s. This discourse of freedom, which centralizes the pursuit of desires, constantly questions sexuality as a fundamental element. In this context, sexuality was always on the agenda in the 1980s, on the one hand as an apolitical and safe commercial field, and on the other as a field of liberation, especially for the women's movement. The magazines' display of the male body serves both dimensions.

This study was conducted by focusing on issues directly related to men in the magazines due to the limits of the article. However, for a complete representation, an analysis of the entire magazines, especially the interviews, and different representations of masculinity would provide a more comprehensive portrayal. Such an analysis also offers the opportunity to trace different types of masculinity existing in the period beyond the ideal male subject in the magazines.

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